

THE IMPACT OF BIBLE TRANSLATION IN THE LINGUISTIC UNIFICATION AND SOCIAL EMPOWERMENT OF ROMA COMMUNITIES

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ABSTRACT: *The impact of Bible translation in the linguistic unification and social empowerment of Roma communities.*

Starting from relevant historical examples, such as the translations during the Reformation period or those in the Romanian area, this paper analyses the efforts to translate the Bible into Romani language, the linguistic and cultural challenges encountered, as well as the socio-cultural impact of this initiative. Through a qualitative and ethnographic approach, the article explores how access to the Scripture in Romani language can contribute to the revitalization of this language, the strengthening of cultural identity and the increase of social cohesion among Roma people.

The research highlights the transformative potential of a Bible translation adapted to the linguistic and cultural context of a vulnerable community.

Keywords: *Roma, Romani language, evangelicals, empowerment*

Introduction

Throughout history, Bible translation has played a fundamental role in shaping the cultural identity and social development of diverse communities. From the spread of Christianity through the Latin Vulgate and the Greek Septuagint to the Reformation - which saw biblical translations into vernacular languages - access to Scripture in the mother tongue democratized religious knowledge by stimulating literacy and contributing to the consolidation of national languages.

In the European context, many languages have undergone significant formalization and enrichment through biblical translation efforts, the example of the Romanian language being eloquent in this respect, where the first widely circulated texts printed¹ were of a religious nature.

This article aims to explore the importance and impact of Bible translation into the common Romani language², providing an important case study for understanding the role of Bible translations in the social development of a minority community. We will examine not only the linguistic and historical aspects of this endeavour, but also the profound socio-cultural implications of having access to the Bible in a clear and relevant form for Roma people.

The research question of this paper - *What is the socio-cultural and linguistic impact of the translation of the Bible into the common Romani language on Roma communities in Romania* - will help us to fulfil the aim of this research paper. In order to answer this question, we propose to analyse the importance of the Holy Scriptures in the emancipation of the Jews and the early church. To understand a historical perspective on the translation of the Bible into Romani language, we will map the efforts to translate the Bible into Romani language. Finally, we will analyse the process and challenges of translating the Bible into the common Romani language and assess the socio-cultural impact of this Bible translation.

¹ *Tetraevangelium* or *Palia of Orăștie, Bucharest Bible* (1688).

² *Common Romani language* is a standardized version of Romani language, created by Roma leaders, linguists and members of international organizations to be understood and used by as many Roma as possible, regardless of the dialect traditionally used. This refers to the idea of unity and comprehensibility between dialects. The common Romani language is based on existing dialects, especially the most widespread ones. This is also called „standard Romani”. From *Cronica rromă (1990-2011)*, [*Romani chronicle (1990-2011)*] by Gheorghe Sarău - Bucharest University Press, 2012, we learn that in 1971, in Orpington, near London, the first World Congress of Roma took place in April 8-12, 1971. Among the stated aims of this congress was the maintenance and development of Roma language and culture. With the 2nd World Roma Congress (8-11 April 1978, Geneva), the efforts to standardize the Romani language were continued, and the language was formalized on 8-11 April 1990 at the 4th Congress of the International Romani Union. In the run-up to the Congress, April 5-7, 1990, a working meeting was held, attended by UNESCO representative Viktor Koptilov, devoted to the standardization of the Romani language, at which recommendations were made and a decision was issued on the alphabet of the Romani language.

The first part of the present paper will analyse the biblical perspective of the importance of Scripture on the first hearers or readers of this influential book for the Judeo-Christian world. We will then explore the impact of biblical translations during the Reformation and the echoes of translation in the Romanian context. We will also address the fragmentary history of the efforts to translate the Bible into Romani language, in various European countries (Bulgaria, England, and Romania).

The central part of the study will focus on analysing the direct impact of current translation on Roma communities, using a qualitative, ethnographic methodology. We will detail the specific linguistic challenges, the methodological steps followed in the translation and research process, the difficulties encountered and, finally, the results and interpretations of the data obtained from the testing among native speakers.

Through this endeavour, we hope to highlight both the linguistic and methodological complexity of such a translation project, as well as its transformative potential for the preservation and revitalization of cultural identity, for education and for strengthening social cohesion among Roma communities.

1. Purpose and importance of Scripture for people

The Bible was written in Hebrew and Aramaic (Old Testament) and Greek (New Testament). The Septuagint (the translation of the Old Testament from Hebrew and Aramaic into Greek) was produced in Egypt, beginning in the 3rd century BC, for the Jews of the diaspora who no longer spoke Hebrew but Koine Greek (the common language of the Mediterranean world at that time). The main aim was to make the Scriptures accessible to a large part of the Jewish community living outside Judaea that had adopted Greek. In this way, this translation aimed to join the bridges to early Christianity, with the Septuagint becoming the Bible of the Christians of the Early Church. The New Testament was written in Greek, and its authors frequently quoted from the Septuagint when referring to the Old Testament. This translation facilitated the rapid spread of Christianity throughout the Hellenistic world.

In this way, it fulfilled the purposes of the Torah - *to purify and elevate human life*³, providing a body of religious teachings to be a per-

³ A. Cohen, *The Talmud*, Bucharest, Hasefer Publishing House, Judaica Collection, 1999, p. 228.

manent guide to life⁴. Scripture, being the source of wisdom, inspires fear of God (the beginning of wisdom⁵), without which society has no morals⁶. The Torah, as interpreted by the Talmud, also has a spiritual purpose with eschatological expressions: *Great is the Torah that gives life to those who practice it, in this world and in the world to come*⁷. The Talmud recommends the Scripture to be applied in daily life, Torah needing to be associated with work.⁸

In the New Testament we find complementary perspectives to the Old Testament. The Bible, in the Apostle's view, is the inspired Word of God, affirming that *All Scripture is God-breathed and is useful for teaching, rebuking, correcting and training in righteousness, so that the servant of God may be thoroughly equipped for every good work*.⁹, being a source of teaching and salvation. The Bible has the purpose to teach people about God, to rebuke them for their sins, to correct them and to prepare them for every good work. It is considered the *word of salvation*¹⁰, having the power to lead people to a new life in Christ.

2. Analysing the impact of Bible translations on the Reformation and its echoes in the Romanian context

With the spread of Christianity in the Western Roman Empire, where Latin was the dominant language, the need for a Bible in this language became evident. The most influential and widespread Latin translation is the Vulgate, by St. Jerome in the late 4th and early 5th centuries. As Latin gradually replaced Greek as the predominant language of the Western Roman Empire, it was essential for the Scriptures to be available in the "vulgar" (common) language for clergy and laity.

The Vulgate became the official Bible of the Catholic Church for more than a thousand years, playing a crucial role in the preservation and transmission of the biblical text throughout the Middle Ages. It served

⁴ A. Cohen, *The Talmud*, p. 226.

⁵ Bible, Psalm 111:10.

⁶ A. Cohen, *op. cit.*, p. 201.

⁷ *Ibidem*, p. 204.

⁸ *Ibidem*, p. 198.

⁹ 2 Timothy 3:16-17.

¹⁰ Acts 13:26.

as the basis for numerous later translations into the vernacular languages of Europe. Another advantage of this standardized translation was that it contributed to a more uniform interpretation of the biblical text and to the consolidation of Christian doctrine in the West.

The impact of translation during the Reformation

Over the ages, the lack of knowledge of Latin was one of the reasons behind the need for a Bible for the common people. The promoters of these initiatives, e.g. Wycliffe¹¹, faced aggressive obstruction from the Catholic Church. This opposition culminated in Martin Luther's success in translating and printing anonymously what was called *the September Testament*. Martin Luther's version of the New Testament, based on the original Greek text, was first published in September 1522 in Wittenberg. Known as the September Testament, the book was entitled "Das Neue Testament Deutzsch" and illustrated with engravings¹². The first printing of 3,000 copies sold out so quickly that a second edition was released in December of the same year. By 1537, the massive success of the book led to the publication of 16 editions. The attractiveness of this translation lay both in its authenticity, given its use of the Greek text, and in the accessible and expressive German language used by Luther, which enabled a wider audience to better understand the message of the New Testament.¹³

Luther is considered a founder of the modern German language through his translation. The translation of the New Testament becomes a true guide to the correct and comprehensible use of a literary language that has been decentred from countless dialects.¹⁴

Due to overwhelming demand, a second edition was needed in December, and 13 years after the first edition, the entire Bible has been published.

¹¹ John Wycliffe (c. 1320-1384) was an English theologian, philosopher, and reformer, considered the „Morning Star of the Protestant Reformation.” He lived nearly two centuries before Martin Luther and challenged many of the doctrines and practices of the Catholic Church at the time, paving the way for the Great Reformation of the 16th century.

¹² Martin Luther, *Writings*, Vol. I, Logos Publishing House, 2003, p. 48.

¹³ Eugen MUNTEANU and Mariana NASTASIA, *Martin LUTHER. Scrisoare deschisă despre traducere [Martin LUTHER. Open Letter on Translating]*, Romanian Academy, Iasi Branch, "A. Philippide" Institute of Romanian Philology Romanian Academy, Iasi Branch, "A. Philippide" Institute of Romanian Philology, 2017, p. 14.

¹⁴ Martin Luther, *op. cit.*, p. 49.

The impact of translation during the Reformation and the post-Reformation period offered the possibility of a democratization of access to the Bible in vernacular languages, influencing the development of national languages. It contributed to the literacy and played a crucial role in social, political and religious changes in Europe.

*The Romanian context of biblical translations
and their impact on education*

These seismic waves of the Reformation were also felt in Romania, where early Bible translations have influenced the development of the Romanian language, culture and national identity. Until the 16th century, religious services in Romania were conducted in Slavonic, a liturgical language that was becoming less and less understood by the common people. This situation created increasing pressure to translate biblical texts into Romanian language, in order to make the Christian message accessible to the people.¹⁵

In the context of the Reformation, the Saxons of Braşov joined forces with the deacon printer Coresi, initiating the translation and printing of religious texts between 1560 and 1582. In the mid-16th century, Braşov, the center of the Protestant Reformation, became the promoter of Romanian printing. The result of the strategic and visionary collaboration between the Saxon Lutheran community and the deacon Coresi had a major impact, marking not only the religious history of Romanians, but also the evolution of the literary language. After the adoption of Lutheranism, the Saxons of Braşov realized the importance of providing the faithful with direct access to the holy texts in their mother tongue. Therefore, between 1560 and 1582, under the aegis of the Braşov magistracy, Coresi printed an impressive series of books. Although they were not the first to be printed in Romanian language, his works, such as the Tetraevanghel or the *Palia* from Orăştie, were particularly popular. They were copied and read in all Romanian provinces, in Transylvania, Wallachia and Moldavia. This wide dissemination contributed decisively to the

¹⁵ First translation by Cornilescu; King Charles II Translation, 1939; Orthodox translation with the approval of the Holy Synod, 1990; GBV 1989; New Testament, fourth edition, trans. Pr. Dr. Emil Pascal - Editions du Dialogue, 1992; Trinitarian Bible Society Translation, 2002 (TBS); Fidela Bible Version, 2015 (Fidela); New Romanian Translation, International Bible Society (Biblica); 2007 (IBS), Roman Catholic Bible Version, 2013 (Cat) 22; Translation of Bartholomew Valerius Ananias, 2001.

unification of the Romanian language. Through the mixture of languages used, Coresi's books provided a linguistic reference model, laying the foundations for the literary Romanian language.

The Bucharest Bible (1688) - "Șerban Cantacuzino's Bible" is undoubtedly the first complete Bible printed in Romanian. Initiated by the ruler Șerban Cantacuzino and finalized by Constantin Brâncoveanu after his death, it was printed at the Snagov Monastery. The translation was carried out by a team of scholars led by brothers Radu and Șerban Greceanu, with the help of Nicolae Milescu Spătarul for the Old Testament (translated from Greek and Latin). The Bucharest Bible was a monumental effort, not only religiously, but also linguistically and culturally.

Similar to the situation during the German Reformation, the Bucharest Bible contributed enormously to the standardization of the Romanian literary language, the spread of written culture and the strengthening of national identity, thus becoming the reference text for centuries.

Emanuel Conțaț mentions that the translation of the Scriptures by the monk priest Dumitru Cornilescu (1924 and 1931) *provoked mixed reactions*¹⁶, ranging from anathematization to captivating reading¹⁷. This explains why in 1925 almost 49,000 Bibles and New Testaments were sold¹⁸. According to the Orthodox priest, Gala Galaction, quoted by Conțaț, the *Bible translated during the Great War by the Protestant neophyte Dimitrie Cornilescu (a former Orthodox hierodeacon) must have been printed, to this day, in half a million copies, of which a small part is still in storage.*¹⁹

Examples of translations of the Holy Scriptures into the dialects of the Romani (Gypsy) language

Translations of the Bible into vernacular languages have also taken place in different dialects of Romani language, in contexts and Roma groups or families in Europe.

We can note, through Bulgarian scholars, that also in the south of the Danube, the first missionary works in Bulgaria took place in 1836,

¹⁶ Emanuel Conțaț, *Din culisele publicării celei mai citite traduceri românești a Sfintei Scripturi*, Oradea, Editura Roua, 2021, p. 95.

¹⁷ *Ibidem*, p. 107.

¹⁸ *Ibidem*, p. 109.

¹⁹ *Ibidem*, p. 110.

by Benjamin Barker of the British and Foreign Bible Society²⁰. Bulgarian evangelical churches appeared in 1903 in the village of Golintsi, near the town of Lom, thanks to the involvement of the Austrian missionary Petar Punchev. From 1910 Punchev began preaching in Romani language. An important moment in the formation of the Roma Baptist Church was the translation of the Gospel of Luke in 1912 into the Erli dialect²¹, becoming the first document translated into a Romani dialect in Bulgaria.

Analysing the evangelical movements in England were closely linked to those in France. The significant moment in the social transformation of the Gypsy Roma Travelers (GRT) in England occurred from 1970, when Pastor Jean Le Cossec sent out his English-speaking missionaries. On this occasion, many GRTs converted to Pentecostalism. Linguist Yaron Matras calls this influence a language revival²².

With the spread of the Life and Light movement in the UK, there have been initiatives to open churches and Bible colleges for nomadic Roma people. Religious materials in audio and video formats, as well as songs with Christian verses in Romani language, have been published for Roma people. The Epistle of Paul to the Romans was translated into the Kalderash dialect in 1980.

Notable attempts can be noticed in the translation of the Bible into different dialects in Germany, Slovenia, Serbia and Slovakia, completing the dialectal bouquet of the Romani language translations of the Bible. All this contributed to the development and maturation of the Romani language, but also had a major impact on Roma people's spirituality and religious life.

²⁰ Alexander Marinov, *Inward Looking: The Impact of Migration on Romanipe from the Romani Perspective*, Berghahn Books, 2019, p. 369.

²¹ The erli dialect is one of the Balkan dialects of Romani language spoken by Roma people in Bulgaria. Among the characteristics of the Balkan dialects, according to Yaron Matras, it would be the following: the form *sine* „he, she was” (third person singular), third person pronoun forms: *ov* „he”, *oj* „she”, *on* „they”, short form of the possessive pronoun: *mo* < *miro* „mine”, *to* < *tiro* „yours”, demonstrative pronouns *akava* „this” (feminine form) and *adava* „this” (masculine form).

²² Matras Yaron, *Romani in Britain: The Afterlife of a Language*, Edinburgh University Press, 2010, p. 159.

3. The impact of translation in Roma communities

In Romania there are several recorded projects to translate the Holy Scriptures into Romani language. One of the earliest attempts was by Gheorghe Vaida, a boilermaker from Brașov county, it is followed by the translation of the New Testament by Luminița Cioabă, under the aegis of SBIR. Other dialectal initiatives were undertaken by the SIL team but abandoned in 2019 in favour of the translation into the Common Romani language carried out by the Committee for the Translation of the Bible into the Common Romani Language and supported by Wycliffe Romania.

The translation initiated by Wycliffe Romania in 2017 represents a linguistic perspective that participates in the unification of dialects, the standardization of the Romani language and aims to smooth the specific challenges of translating religious concepts into a language with a less developed written tradition.

This could explain what has been mentioned in an interview with Prof. Viorel Achim during doctoral research²³, that *translating the Bible into a language marks the maturity of that language*.

On the occasion of the same academic itinerary, to investigate The Role of the Church in the Transformation of Roma Churches in South-Eastern Romania after 1990²⁴, Professor Gheorghe Sarău, mentioned that *although the non-Protestant cults faced many restrictions from the communist institutions, nevertheless, during that period there were constant concerns among the Roma believers to translate the holy word*²⁵. The examples given by Sarău are multiple: mentioning Vaida Gheorghe (father) and Vaida Ioan (son) from Ormeniș - Brașov, who translated the Gospel of Mark, this initiative was joined immediately after 1990 by the Interconfessional Bible Society of Romania (SBIR). Among the several projects for the translation and editing of the Gospels, initiated with the assistance of Vasile Roske, Ioan Caraza, Robert F. Rice (Tulsa - USA), Paul Ellingworth (from the United Bible Societies of London), the above-mentioned contribution was among the publications - starting in 1996.

Profesor Sarău mentioned that in the post-Decembrist period, with the encouragement of the SBIR and other religious entities, a series of

²³ Rafael Năstase, *Ecceromo*, Bucharest University Press, 2025.

²⁴ Rafael Năstase, *op. cit.*

²⁵ Mention belongs to Prof. Gheorghe Sarău during the researcher's doctoral research.

translations and books in a biblical context appeared, such as *Marco* [= Gospel of Mark] 1996, *Evanghelia pala o Marco. Romani (the Kalderash)*²⁶. The next initiative also mentioned by Profesor Sarău is Matei [= Gospel of Matthew] 1996, *Evanghelia pala o Matei. Rromani (Ursari dialect)*.²⁷

Also, from Gheorghe Sarău we learn, from a personal communication made in March 2024, the following:

“Unfortunately, three other SBIR projects remained unfinished, in the sense that, although the manuscripts were elaborated, the works were not edited, being the translation of the “Gospel of John”, realized by the Romani kalderash writer Camelia Stănescu, the two of them benefiting from methodical guidance, at SBIR headquarters, from the nonagenarian Robert F. Rice (from Tulsa - USA).

Similarly, the two translators undertook the translation and adaptation from English into Romani language of a book of biblical stories, “*Po but dud - More Light*”, also at the request and with funding from SBIR. According to the distinguished Professor, this has not been published either.

After 1997, other initiatives to publish biblical translations and to write and print other books of this kind were visible. With the help of Pastor and university Professor Otniel Bunaciu and the “Providența” Church in Bucharest, a collection of biblical texts in Romani language, translated by Professor Gheorghe Sarău have been published.²⁸

²⁶ Reviewers on behalf of UBS = United Bible Societies: Prof. Dr. Donald Kenrick [and *Word to the Readers*], Prof. Dr. Paul Ellingworth. Reviewer from the Interdenominational Bible Society of Romania: Rev. Bakó Béla. Coordinators on behalf of the Interconfessional Bible Society of Romania: Cristian Vasile Roske; Eleonora Galgotzi], Bucharest: [Printisardo catar e Societatea Biblică Interconfesională a României], 1996, 77 + 3 p. Translators: Gheorghe Vaida and Ioan Vaida.

²⁷ Bucharest: Societatea Biblică Interconfesională anda-i România [Printisardo catar e...], 1996, 107 p. + 5 p.); Reviewers on behalf of UBS = United Bible Societies: prof. dr. Donald Kenrick, prof. dr. Paul Ellingworth. Reviewers from SBIR = Societatea Biblică Interconfesională din România [Interconfessional Bible Society of Romania]: Rev. Pál; prof. Gheorghe Sarău; Coordinators for the Interconfessional Bible Society of Romania: Cristian Vasile Roske; Eleonora Galgotzi”. Translator: Ștefan Bărniș.

²⁸ *Biblikane teksturenqo kidipen anθ-i rromani çhib* [Collection of biblical texts in Romani language], Bucharest: Kriterion Publishing House, VIII p. + 134 p., 2002. „The manual „Culegere de texte biblice în Rromani» [Collection of biblical texts in Romani language] was published on the initiative of the translator *Gheorghe Sarău*, with the moral and financial support of the Providence Foundation of Bucharest. Translator: Prof. Dr. *Gheorghe Sarău*, illustrations and cover by the Roma painter: *Eugen Raportoru*».

It is important to mention the remarkable work of the Roma writer and activist Luminița Cioabă, including a translation of the Bible into the Kalderash dialect of the Romani language. Known as “E Romaii Biblia 2020 (Kăldărăhko)” or KALD2020, this edition was published in 2020 and is based on the popular Romanian version by Cornilescu. Produced in partnership with the British and Foreign Bible Society of London and the Interdenominational Bible Society of Romania, the translation is of profound cultural significance, providing the Kalderash Roma community with access to sacred texts in their mother tongue and thus contributing to the preservation of their linguistic identity. The book is also available in digital format on applications such as YouVersion.²⁹

A final example is the *Gospel of Luke*, translated by Sorin-Cristian Moiescu into the Spoitori dialect³⁰, and a collection of biblical texts by the same author also in the Spoitori dialect (Hădărește)³¹.

Thus, we can speak of an incredible production of publishing, media (magazines and leaflets, radio programs, internet, online postings and storages, etc.) promoting biblical texts in the common Romani language and in different local varieties of the Romani language.

Translating the Bible into the Common Romani language, case study

In the following we will give a detailed account of the process of translating the Bible into the Common Romani language.

As mentioned above, the translation of the Bible into the common Romani language is not just another dialectal translation but represents - from the linguistic point of view - the unification of dialects and the standardization of the Romani language, and from the theological point of view - a standardization of dogmatic religious concepts in a language with a less developed written tradition.

²⁹ [https://www.bible.com/audio-bible-app-versions/3114-kald2020-kalderash-romani-cornilescu-bible-2020-\(romania\)](https://www.bible.com/audio-bible-app-versions/3114-kald2020-kalderash-romani-cornilescu-bible-2020-(romania)), accessed on August 15.

³⁰ Sorin-Cristian Moiescu, *I Mujdes Katar o Lukas Tradusi Kerzi romanes hidirca* [The Gospel according to Luke translated into Romani Hădărească - Romani language, Romani literature, lexicon], Brașov: Etnous Publishing House, 2025.

³¹ *Idem*, *Andral O Kutsal Ketapi, romanes, hidirca* [From the Holy Book, in the Romani Hădărească] - Romani language, Romani literature, lexicon], Brașov: Etnous Publishing House, 2025.

Stages of the process of translating the Bible into the common Romani language: from the identification of key words to publication

In this section of the article, we aim to present how the translation of the Bible into the Common Romani language is carried out, detailing the stages of the translation process as well as the key roles of the people involved in the project (translators, testers, exegetes, consultants, etc.).

It is important to note that both the principles of translation and the structure of the steps followed by translators of the Common Romani Bible are based on³² Katharina Barnwell's course, *Translating the Bible - an introductory course for native translators*³³. The methodology of translating the Bible into Romani language briefly includes key word identification, oral and written translation, comprehensibility testing, proof-reading (individual, team, exegetical), and preparation for publication. Each stage contributes to ensuring the theological coherence, clarity and linguistic naturalness of the text.

According to Barnwell³⁴, the order in which the stages of the translation process take place may vary from project to project, depending on the specifics of the team involved and the cultural and linguistic context of the target community.

1. Identifying key words

Bible translation begins with a terminological analysis of the selected passage. The chapter to be translated is searched for in the Paratext software³⁵, using the *Biblical Terms* tool to identify untranslated terms, marked with X, and to assess their consistency throughout the corpus. Several relevant translations are consulted for context (by selecting the "Comparative Text" option), and other Romani translations are used for additional ideas.

³² Katharina Barnwell's course has been developed from fundamental works in the field of biblical translation, such as *The Theory and Practice of Translation*, by E.A. Nida and C.R. Taber and *Translating the Word of God* by J. Beekman and J.C. Callow.

³³ Katharina Barnwell, *Translating the Bible - An Introductory Course for Mother Tongue Translators*, Wycliffe Romania Association, 2017, translated into Romanian by Ina Bulzan, p. 249.

³⁴ Katharina Barnwell, *Translating the Bible*, p. 249.

³⁵ Paratext is a software used for translating, revising and creating Bible studies, developed by UBS (United Bible Societies) and SIL (*Summer Institute of Linguistics*) International.

Attention is given to spelling, diacritics and the correct form of words, as the program does not recognize wrong variants. It is also recommended to introduce the basic form of words (root without suffixes), accompanied by a literal translation into Romanian and, where appropriate, into English for consultants. Terms are added to the glossary, together with definitions and supporting notes. If a term is not considered appropriate, it shall be explained in the "Description" field, together with the reason for rejection.

2. Oral translation: preparation and execution

This translation method exploits the oral nature of many minority languages and cultures. The text is broken up into short units (2-5 verses) to make it easier to memorize, and translators consult several modern translations for meaning (e.g. *The New Testament for Everyone*, *The Living Word*, *The Bible in the updated version*, etc.).

Translation is done by storytelling³⁶, without visual access to the written sources. Several versions are voice-recorded, and the clearest and most natural is later transcribed. According to Barnwell, this method of translation improves the accuracy of the text.

At this stage, translators also required the following:

- They consult the available exegetical notes and clarify any uncertainties before starting the translation.
- Analyse the emotions and motivations of the characters, identify the relevant climax and stylistic devices.
- Optionally, make drawings of the verses, marking key words in Romani language.
- Play the content through oral storytelling, without consulting the Romanian translations, recording 2-3 different versions.
- Listen to the recordings and retell as many times as necessary (up to 4-8 times).

³⁶ Katharina Barnwell, *op. cit.*, p. 130: „Many find it very helpful to work out the first draft of a translation in this way: first they study the source text so that they have its meaning clear in their minds. They then retell in their own words without looking into the source text. They record this version. They then transcribe this version and work on this draft, improving its accuracy.”

- ✦ They transcribe the final version into Paratext, to be improved with ideas from other recordings.

3. *Written translation (first draft)*

If the written method is chosen, the translation is done by consulting the original version and 3-5 modern translations in parallel. Resources such as <https://www.bible.com/> or interdenominational projects are used. Translators also consult exegetical notes³⁷, check parallel passages³⁸ and compare existing translations. After editing, the written translation is narrated to test the naturalness of expression. If there are significant discrepancies, the translators revisit the text.³⁹

4. Translation verification

A very important role in Bible translation plays the verification. Is essential to ensure the quality, accuracy and fidelity of the final text. Through a rigorous evaluation process, any errors are corrected, the original meaning of the message is preserved, and the text is clear and accessible to speakers of the target language. In this way, translation becomes an effective communication tool in connection with the linguistic and cultural tradition of the community. According to Barnwell, verification is a tedious but necessary task.⁴⁰

4.1. Individual checking⁴¹

In the individual checking stage, the translator assesses whether the text is clear, natural and faithful to the original meaning. A sentence-by-sentence comparison is made using a reference translation (such as EDCR⁴²) to identify omissions, additions or changes in meaning.

It also checks spelling, correct use of keywords, and consistency of headings and footnotes⁴³. Various corrections can be made to the text at

³⁷ Translators consult the exegetical decisions if they can't find very clear answers at <https://faithbridge.multilingualai.com/login/>

³⁸ By accessing the Parallel Passages button in Paratext, it is recommended to check for differences and similarities in the original or in various translations.

³⁹ Katharina Barnwell, *op. cit.*, p. 130.

⁴⁰ *Ibidem*, p. 200.

⁴¹ first check.

⁴² Dumitru Cornilescu Revised Edition.

⁴³ If the translator finds problems with the comprehension of the text for a common listener/reader (because the historical or cultural context is very different), he/she will

this stage: omitted words or phrases are added and those incorrectly inserted by the translator are removed.⁴⁴

Also, as part of the individual check, translators will keep track of the established keywords. If these words have been used, they appear ticked in the *Biblical Keywords* tool filtered by chapter. If better keywords than those initially set are identified, these can be entered into the *Bible Keywords* with a note to that effect.

4.2. Second check

After a break of a few days, the text is read in the presence of another person able to understand the language and who gives feedback on clarity and coherence. Here, unclear expressions/words are corrected, and problems are noted for discussion in the *exegetical checking* stage.

4.3. Exegetical checking

In this stage, the exegetes offer comments on the theological and semantic meaning. The team responds only to accepted or clear notes. The rest of the issues are discussed in Zoom or face-to-face sessions.

4.4. Checking keywords

In the keyword checking stage, it is confirmed that all keywords are translated uniformly, are correctly marked in Paratext and have an appropriate definition in the glossary. Explanatory notes and dialect differences are recorded. Terms are also checked for clear English and Romanian translations. Where necessary, the glossary is also completed.

4.5. Team verification

In the team check, in the first phase the translators read the chapters assigned to the others and leave notes for the translator where they think the translation is not clear, accurate or natural, and in the second phase the team goes through the text verse by verse together. This is where the team intervenes only in situations of vagueness, looking for coherence and naturalness of wording.

insert a footnote. In many situations it is preferable to have the explanations in the text, as listeners will not have access to the footnotes and most readers will ignore them.

⁴⁴ If more than one problem is identified, it is recommended that the text be re-translated and re-checked.

5. Translation testing

According to Barnwell, testing means giving the translation to other speakers of the language, external to the translation team, to see whether it makes sense to them and whether the message communicated is the correct one.⁴⁵

5.1. Question preparation

Based on the instructions in Barnwell, comprehensibility test questions are developed and expected answers are established. How this is done can be seen in the Appendix (test document).

5.2. Actual testing

At least two people from the community are involved in the actual testing. The results are recorded in Paratext, and the feedback is analysed by the team, and improvements to the text are proposed.

Below, as an example, is one of the experiences during a test. To the question developed in sub-stage 5.1 - *Question preparation* [*Kaj sas ingerdo o Isus katar o Duho?* “Where was Jesus taken by the Spirit”), during two tests, the first one carried out on 01.02.2024 and the second one on 15.03.2025, the following answers were recorded:

Volunteer	Answer	Expected answer
D. B., 17 years old, native speaker	And-o than le mulenqo. (literally: In the place of the dead.)	O Jesus sar ingerdo katar o Duho and-o mulano than. ([...] <i>Jesus was led by the Spirit into the wilderness</i>) ⁴⁶
E. K., 35, native speaker	And-o mulano than. (Literal: In the dead/de- serted place.)	O Jesus sar ingerdo katar o Duho and-o mulano than. ([...] <i>Jesus was led by the Spirit into the wilderness</i>)

Again, the team marks mistakes, hesitations and so on in the text, and volunteers identify strange expressions or misunderstood words in the translated text. For example, after reading the passage about Jesus' entry

⁴⁵ Katharina Barnwell, *op. cit.*, p. 200.

⁴⁶ Gospel of Matthew, chapter 4: 1.

into Capernaum⁴⁷ in Matthew 4:12-14, the two volunteers pointed out several issues:

Volunteer	Comments
D. B., 17, native speaker	- by telărdăs “(he) went away” he means te jas/te inklîos “to go in/to go out”; - suggests: phirdea(s) „he walked, moved around”.
E. K., 35, native speaker	- suggests, instead of režiuni “regions”, bare thana “big places”; - proposes, instead of pherdöl “fills, fulfills”, pherdöl pes ⁴⁸ “fills, fulfills”; - mentions that pand-o “through, by means of” does not exist in his spoken dialect, but has deduced from the text that it could be the preposition andar „from, through, by means of”.

5.3. Review and retesting

At this stage, the notes are discussed individually and as a team. The translator reviews the individual notes. The modified verses are retested to validate the new versions. Results are added to Paratext.

5.4. Testing additional material

The Committee for the Standard Romani Bible Translation emphasized the need for a glossary to include terms less familiar to some speakers. These terms can play an essential role in the preservation of the Romani language, which is why it is important for them to be promoted, together with their corresponding synonyms in other dialects, so that every speaker can find his or her way around the biblical text.

At this stage, both the glossary and other additional materials are tested separately as a team to ensure accessibility and informational relevance.

⁴⁷ *Kana așundăs ke o Joan sasasas phandado, o Jesus gelo gelo Pesqe and-e Galilee. Telărdăs andar o Nazaret haj avilăs te beșel and-o foro Kapernaum, pašal o baro pani Genezaret, and-ol režiuni Zabulon haj Neftali, kaș te pherel pes so sas phendo pand-o prooroko Isaja [...]* [When Jesus heard that John had been put in prison, he withdrew to Galilee. Leaving Nazareth, he went and lived in Capernaum, which was by the lake in the area of Zebulun and Naphtali - to fulfill what was said through the prophet Isaiah].

⁴⁸ *pherdöl pes* represents a dialectal variant specific to certain speakers with the value of a double reflexive, which was rejected by the team.

6. Preparing for and checking with the consultant

After testing, biblical terms are updated and the *back translation*⁴⁹ is generated in Paratext. Any preliminary questions from the consultant⁵⁰ are answered and comments are entered into Paratext, after which the final check - which involves online or face-to-face meetings with the authorized consultant and is mandatory for any translation to be published. Translators act as mediators between the consultant and the speakers of the target language, without influencing their answers. The consultant asks questions to check the fidelity and clarity of the text, and the translation is adjusted according to the results obtained⁵¹. This stage is essential to validate the

⁴⁹ In Matthew 1:25, the expression „he did not know her” has been translated into Romani language as „na sutăș pesqe laça” [literally: „he did not sleep with her”]. The consultant asked the following question to the translators after checking the back-translation: Was the verb „did not know her” also tried? I ask only to remain faithful to the GRK and the English texts. In the Greek as well as Hebrew of the biblical text it has an intimate connotation, referring to conjugal relations in order to have children. A translator replied: „It is an idiomatic expression in the Romanian, but in the Romani it would be understood that he did not see her face to face”. Therefore, the expression „na sutăș pesqe laça” was validated.

⁵⁰ „The task of a translation consultant is to help the team to ensure that the translation made is accurate and clear. Any Bible translation that will be published must be checked by a consultant. He or she will work with the team and ask questions to be considered.” (from K. Barnwell, *op. cit.*, p. 202).

⁵¹ Concerning the translation of a word in Matthew 2:2, the consultant noted the following: „τεχθεις» is the past participle of the verb «to be born» and clearly refers to the birth of «the king», not a «child» in the usual sense. The focus of the GRK text, like the verses you are following, is on the birth of the King, not the Child. How can you point this out? You might try: «Where is the King of the Jews, (the Infant) who was born?»- even though he was only a Baby, this King was a cause of great distress to Herod and to all in Jerusalem who heard about Him. The translators agreed with this proposal and changed the translation.

Concerning Matthew 2:22, the consultant continued: in verses 13, 19, 20 “an angel of the Lord appeared to Joseph in a dream”. From the account it would be understandable that the same angel said to him in a dream. If it cannot be translated in a passive form: “Joseph feared to go into Judea, and when it **was spoken to him in a dream**”..., then replace the word God with “the angel of God”. Also, concerning Matthew 3:9 the consultant pointed out that “the Greek expression does not affirm Abraham’s identity as *father*, but rather claims the descent from him, which is different. In the Romanian back translation, is it claiming descent from Abraham or paternity from Abraham? If in the TBRS (Translation of the Bible into Romani Standard Version) it is not understood that Abraham is the father, but it declares descent, that’s fine!”. The consultant’s interventions were extremely helpful to the translators, so they improved the translation.

translation before publication. The consultant can work in Romanian or English, and in some cases, the exegete translates into Google documents.

7. Preparing for publication

After checking with the consultant, the necessary changes are made. Auxiliary materials are finalized and the consistency of key words is checked again. The text is prepared for publication according to the international standards of Bible translation organizations (e.g. SIL).

Four translators from different religious denominations (Baptist, Pentecostal, Orthodox) and speakers of different dialects (Ursari, Kalde-rash, Carpathian) are involved in the process of translating the Bible into the Common Romani language. The team is supplemented by several testers and verifiers, two Scripture exegetes and a specialized consultant.

As of fall 2021, the *Gospel of John*⁵², the *Gospel of Mark*⁵³ and *Acts*⁵⁴ have been translated and published, while *the Gospel of Matthew* and *the Gospel of Luke* are in the process of translation.

One of the main difficulties encountered by the translators and other members of the team translating the Bible into Romani language is the lack of equivalent terms in that language for complex biblical concepts. In many cases, the creation of new words is not a viable option either, as some speakers are reluctant to use new or borrowed terms from other languages, considering them alien to the Romani linguistic identity. Some members of traditionalist Roma communities tend to overestimate their own dialect, perceiving it as the authentic form of Romani, and may reject variants that depart from it. Thus, any form that does not resemble their own dialect is often considered not to be authentic “Romani”.

Difficulties encountered during the research

As mentioned, one of the very important stages of the translation process is testing. TBRC members (translators, Chairman, Executive Director or members of the Translation Committee) go to different Roma communities speaking different dialects present in Romania. One of the difficulties encountered in the communities is that of initial reluctance,

⁵² Romani version: *E Evangelia pala o Joan.*

⁵³ Romani version: *E Evangelia pal-o Marku.*

⁵⁴ Romani version: *So kerde ol Apostolă.*

justified by *we don't speak common Romani or it's not my language*. After a careful reading or listening of the text (when it is done with the audio versions of the translation), the tested speakers realize the accuracy of the text, its correct form and, at the same time, some linguistic differences coming from the dilution of the language by introducing Romanian words (in the case of the Ursari dialect) or Hungarian words (when we talk about the Gabor dialect or the Carpathian dialect).

Another difficulty observed is related to the cursive reading of biblical texts by Roma, due to characters not found in Romanian.⁵⁵

It should be mentioned that one of the tests was carried out by the members of the Committee at the *Roma Christian Networks Conference* in Dures-Albania in 2024. The reading of verse 16 of chapter 3 of the Gospel of John, for an audience of 150 people, mostly Roma people from Europe. Another test was also carried out by the Committee members in several Orthodox and Muslim Roma communities in the Burgas area (Bulgaria). As they could either not read at all or could only read Bulgarian Cyrillic characters, they were given the opportunity to listen to texts from John, Mark and Acts. Some respondents said they could understand between 70%-80%, others said they could not understand words like *grace*.⁵⁶

It was unexpected but joyful moment when various Roma people from Europe proved to understand the common version from Romania. In order to see the impact of this translation, other pilot bilingual test are ongoing in Spain and in France, using Romani Common Bible Translation. This represents future research project to measure the impact.

Conclusions

As we see, the translation of the Bible into Romani language is an act of fundamental importance, which has a profound impact on the social and

⁵⁵ 3 - read as Romanian *ge, gi*; e.g. 3amutro (*giamutro* or *jamutro*) - son-in-law; θ - read as Romanian *t*, respectively *d*, used only in locative-ablative postpositions; e.g: *gavesθar* (*gavestar*) «from the village», *gavenθe* (*gavende*) «in the villages»; Ç - is read as a Romanian *s*, respectively *ș*, used only in sociative-instrumental postpositions; e.g.: *grasteça* (*grastesa*) «with the horse», *grastença* (*grastența*) «with the horses»;

⁵⁶ *dinipen* „gift, grace”, but in some dialects it can also mean „quarrel” (from *del pes* „to quarrel”).

cultural development of Roma communities. This process is more than a mere linguistic exercise, it is an affirmation of dignity, a validation of identity and a catalyst for positive changes.

When people can read their sacred texts in their own language, it strengthens their sense of belonging, contributes to literacy and helps them to be more united.

The theological reflection of this article can be analysed by comparing with the perspectives of representative theologians such as Kwame Bediako and Andrew F. Walls, which provide a solid basis for understanding why this translation is so crucial.

Kwame Bediako argues that Scripture in the mother tongue enables the Gospel to authentically “dwell” in the heart of a culture⁵⁷. Therefore, a Romani Bible is not just a religious text but becomes an intrinsic part of Roma cultural heritage. By reading the Word of God in their own language, Roma people can interact with the biblical message in a personal and relevant way, transforming it into a guide for their daily life and their relationship with God. Also in the Bible, they find values that transcend time and space, in terms of the role of the family in society, of women, men and respect for authority. This approach removes linguistic and cultural barriers, allowing a deeper understanding of faith.

An accessible and universal divine language

One of the strongest arguments in favour of Bible translation comes from the theological concept of incarnation. As Andrew F. Walls has noted, the act of Christ, divine, becoming human is the ultimate model of intercultural communication⁵⁸. This idea emphasizes that the Christian faith is “infinitely culturally translatable” and rejects the notion of an exclusive sacred language. The Romani language translation therefore confirms that the Bible, whatever the language, remains the Word of God. It promotes equality between languages and cultures, conferring dignity on Romani speakers who are recognized as having a language capable of expressing divine truths.

⁵⁷ Kwame Bediako, *Christianity in Africa: The Renewal of a Non-Western Religion*, Edinburgh University Press, 1995, p. 61.

⁵⁸ Andrew F. Walls, *The Missionary Movement in Christian History: Studies in the Transmission of Faith*, New York, Orbis Books, 1996, pp. 26-29.

In this way, the Bible translation satisfies divine justice, affirming the dignity of all humans created in the image of God. Translating the Bible into Romani is not simply an exercise in transcribing words, but an act of social and spiritual justice that legitimizes Romani language and culture.

Impact on community identity and development

The translation of Scripture into Romani language has profound implications for identity and social cohesion. As Bediako suggests, the Bible becomes a *context that people inhabit and participate in* through their mother tongue⁵⁹. Therefore, translation not only provides access to a source of spirituality, but also contributes to the reinforcement of Roma cultural identity by giving them a common point of reference and a set of ethical values.

In conclusion, a Roma Bible is not a mere translation project but an engine of transformation. It encourages literacy, preserves and promotes the Romani language, thus contributing to cultural revitalization. By providing a source of inspiration and spiritual guidance in a familiar language, Bible translation gives the Roma community a powerful tool to develop socially, culturally and spiritually. This is an essential step in enabling them to assert themselves, find their place in the world and participate actively in society without losing their cultural richness.

To conclude this article, we would like to recommend promoting the use of translation. Wider distribution is essential, not only online (YouVersion app) but also in print. Key partners in disseminating this translation are Roma churches and non-governmental organizations. These partners could ensure effective dissemination and thus increase literacy rates.

In order to disseminate this translation, we believe that by creating teaching materials such as the translation can serve as a basis for the development of textbooks and educational resources to support the teaching and learning of Romani language, both in schools and in community programs.

As the illiteracy rate⁶⁰ in Romania is very high among the Roma population, and school drop-out⁶¹ is higher compared to the majority

⁵⁹ Kwame Bediako, *The African Renaissance and Theological Reconstruction*, p. 31.

⁶⁰ According to a European Commission report in 2008, the illiteracy rate among the Roma population in Romania was 28%, an alarmingly high figure which highlights the profound disparities in access to education. European Commission, „National Strategy Report” (2006-2008).

⁶¹ A study conducted by Roma Education Fund Romania (2013) shows that the dropout rate in secondary school for Roma students is 31%, compared to only 7% for

population, the development of audio and video resources is impetuously needed. Given the oral nature of many dialects, the creation of audio (audio bibles, religious songs) and video materials could increase the accessibility and impact of translation, especially for those who cannot read.

We recommend detailed sociological research in the future which could assess to what extent translation into the common Romani language influences the alignment of local dialects and the acceptance of a standardized form of the language.

Furthermore, a qualitative study, through interviews and focus groups, could also explore in other Roma communities in Romania and other countries how community members perceive the contribution of translation in strengthening cultural identity and promoting unity among different Roma groups (Kalderash, Gabors, Ursari, Spoitori, etc.). In this way, we could have a clearer understanding of the causes of possible strategies to overcome linguistic and cultural barriers.

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non-Roma students. This statistic is also confirmed by more recent reports, such as the one by the organization Save the Children Romania (2024), which shows that only 22% of Roma children continue their high school education, in contrast to 80% of the majority population. Mediafax, „Roma children are six times more at risk of dropping out of school”, Save the Children Romania, „Only 22% of Roma children attend high school”.

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Web links

- ✦ <https://ec.europa.eu/social/BlobServlet?docId=2622&langId=ro>
- ✦ <https://www.mediafax.ro/social/copiii-romi-au-risc-de-sase-ori-mai-mare-decat-ceilalti-sa-abandoneze-scoala-11253136>
- ✦ <https://www.salvaticopiii.ro/sites/ro/files/2024-04/doar-22-dintre-copiii-romi-urmeaza-studii-liceale-comparativ-cu-populatia-majoritara-unde-ponderea-urca-la-80.pdf>
- ✦ <https://biblia-rromani.ro/>
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Annex

Test document .⁶²

I. Entire section

A. Read the section (volunteer or translators).

Before reading the section, remind the volunteer that a question about the topic of the section will follow.

Text:

B. Questions about the section

What is the most important thing the author wants to say here?
[Theme, main idea].

Expected answer:

II. Read the verses from Matthew 4:15-16

Before reading, remind the volunteer that a question about the theme of the section will follow.

Mark mistakes, hesitations or any changes in the text!

Ask if there are any difficult/ununderstood words in the text, or anything strange!

Problem words:

A. Retelling

Ask the volunteer to tell in their own words what has been read.

Check if there are things added, omitted or changed! Note any phrases/words that might be helpful!

B. Questions per verse

Verse

Question:

Expected answer:

⁶² Prepared according to Katharina Barnwell, *op. cit.*, pp. 206-208.